

>>”Abortion is about body autonomy and is therefore Libertarian”

In this letter:

- A rational rebuttal of the idea that abortion is Libertarian
- An explication of the socialist pathogen in Eugenic action
- Revealing the far left [Marxis] attack upon the institutions of the Republic (until recently known as) the United States of America
- An Appendix chocked full of POS postings.

POS 1.01 - No, Roe v Wade is not Libertarian¹

Or, exposing the bare facts of a Human Flesh Industry staple, replete with propaganda so extreme, you have people foaming out of the mouth in order to defend it. Forget Vietnam veterans, these are literal “baby-killers”

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¹ And please, no lies about states’ rights and the Civil War. Libertarians were not around then, and at any rate, if you will refer to the Civil Rights Act of 1871, you will see which party was in support of slavery (and then Jim Crow). And no, there was no party switch (it was 2 senators).

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Dear Readers,

Actually, no. Roe v. Wade isn't giving any rights. That would amount to the idea that women, a single group, received an extratemporaneous right to commit homicide, and no other group has as many rights, and that babies have even fewer rights than normal people. It is true they don't yet have full rights; but their nascent born rights for being human are the same in volume. Roe v. Wade was a *bad ruling*, because it:

1. Deregulated homicide using Federal power, which violated the 10th Amendment (ie, States' rights)
 - a. Homicide definition: *"Homicide is when one human being causes the death of another. Not all homicide is murder, as some killings are manslaughter, and some are lawful, such as when justified by an affirmative defense, like insanity or self-defense. criminal law."*²
 - b. Homicide etymology:
 - i. *"Middle English: from Old French, from Latin homicidium, from homo, homin-'man'."*
 - ii. *"the killing of another person," early 13c., from Old French homicide, from Latin homicidium "manslaughter," from homo "man" (see [homunculus](#)) + -cidium "act of killing," from caedere "to kill, to cut down" (from PIE root *kae-id- "to strike"). The meaning "person who kills another" (late 14c.) also is from French (homicide), from Latin homicida "a murderer," from homo + -cida "killer." Identical in French and English, the two words differ in Latin and in other languages (for example, Spanish homicida/homicidio)."*³
 - c. In order to prove abortion is not (at minimum) a homicide, one would need to prove that a fetus is *other than* a homo sapiens sapiens. (i.e., a hybrid)
2. Created class distinctions with women having a special 'right' that no one other group has, which victimized a particular group and violated the rights of the greatest minority possible: the individual (and in this case, completely innocent).
 - a. No, the fetus is not committing assault, as shall be shown in another section.
 - b. Yes, abortion "rights" has roots in atheistic and Marxist (and therefore a National Security threat) attack on women, the family, Judeo-Christianity, and...
 - c. Yes, it has racist origins, particularly with Margaret Sanger, a eugenicist.⁴
 - d. So Yes, it was and is genocide⁵ and eugenicide:
 - i. First of black 'African-Americans' who receive a disproportionately high rate of the heinous procedure⁶, which should only be performed for emergencies and highly regulated (as any planned death is/should be)

² <https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/homicide>

³ <https://www.etymonline.com/word/homicide>

⁴

<https://www.usatoday.com/story/opinion/2020/07/23/racism-eugenics-margaret-sanger-deserves-no-honors-column/5480192002/>

⁵ <https://fightingmonarch.com/2020/07/21/planned-parenthood-supports-genocide/>

⁶ ~11-13% of population getting 33% of the abortions. Or more.

<https://www.extremelyamerican.com/post/planned-parenthood-government-corporate-funded-genocide-of-american-black-babies>

- ii. Now, of white Americans⁷, who receive the largest number by volume⁸.
 - iii. Both constitute a Clear and Present Danger⁹ to America itself, in the form of economic and National Security “strategic” matters; not explained in over detail in this paper, only cursorily.
 - iv. Therefore the government has a right and a duty to defend itself and the Nation from the Roe v Wade ruling itself.
 1. At this point, of course, Congress has failed to do its duty¹⁰ and clarify the matter with a $\frac{2}{3}$ majority amendment¹¹.
 - e. The 9th amendment is not violated by the change in ruling.
 - i. *“The enumeration in the Constitution, of certain rights, shall not be construed to deny or disparage others retained by the people.”¹²*
 - ii. Homicide is not a right, nor a ‘certain right’
 1. Police acting in self-defense or defense of others is highly regulated homicide
 2. Soldiers acting in self-defense or under orders is highly regulated homicide
 3. All homicide in self-defense is *highly regulated homicide*.
 - iii. Abortion **disparages the rights of the fetus.**
 1. Fetuses have ‘certain rights’: *“In 1999, the [Unborn Victims of Violence Act](#) was introduced into [United States Congress](#) which defines violent [assault](#) committed against pregnant women as being a [crime](#) against two victims: the woman and the fetus she carries.^[75] This law was passed in 2004 after the [murder of Laci Peterson](#) and the fetus she was carrying. In 2002, U.S. [President George W. Bush](#) announced a plan to ensure [health care](#) coverage for fetuses under the [State Children's Health Insurance Program \(CHIP\)](#).”^{13 14}*
3. Violated Clear & Present Danger doctrine
 - a. Under which the following are more clearly understood:
 - i. Rape - an abortion would be considered retroactive self-defense to prevent PTSD and/or suicide.
 - ii. Incest - an abortion would literally protect both parties from genetic diseases and, again, PTSD.
 - iii. Situations, abnormal as they are, which present a danger to the life of the mother and/or child, creating a right to fight to preserve life which a jury of reasonable peers (and not fundamentalists, for example) would agree exceeds the right to life and ‘body autonomy’ of the fetus.

⁷ See: Amanda Duarte below

⁸ ~35-40 million of the 55 million

⁹ http://www.johnstonsarchive.net/policy/abortion/usa_abortion_by_race.html

¹⁰ <https://19thnews.org/2022/01/congress-codify-abortion-roe/>

¹¹ <https://www.wbpscups.com/amendment-types-of-majority-in-parliament/>

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ninth_Amendment_to_the_United_States_Constitution

¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fetal_rights

¹⁴ <https://www.ncsl.org/research/health/fetal-homicide-state-laws.aspx>

4. Creates a fake identity of the fetus as a form of property by denying body autonomy to the fetus on the unusual account of symbiotic (and natural) relationship and reliability of the mother (fit or unfit as the case may be).
 - a. Humans cannot be property (i.e., slaves): *“Neither slavery nor involuntary servitude, except as a punishment for crime whereof the party shall have been duly convicted, shall exist within the United States, or any place subject to their jurisdiction.”* ~13th amendment to the Constitution of the United States of America
 - i. A fetus has never committed a crime and so cannot be punished.
 - ii. The fetus’ own involuntary servitude is invalid because of the natural symbiotic relationship with the mother.
 - iii. Neither party can hold slavery of the other
 - iv. Both parties have body autonomy
 - v. Temporary conditions of dependency do not abrogate God Given Rights (i.e. Human Rights under Geneva Conventions)
 - b. *“All persons born or naturalized in the United States and subject to the jurisdiction thereof, are citizens of the United States and of the State wherein they reside. No State shall make or enforce any law which shall abridge the privileges or immunities of citizens of the United States; nor shall any State **deprive any person of life, liberty, or property, without due process of law;** nor deny to any person within its jurisdiction **the equal protection of the laws.**”* ~14th Amendment, section 1
 - i. Therefore laws which create special ‘abortion rights’ are likely to be subject to violations of the 14th Amendment, which will supercede the 9th Amendment, as all newer amendments correct and clarify previous amendments.
5. Draws from other amendments to invent a form of Privacy which does not exist, explicit as such, in the 9th or 14th amendments.

More than a ‘Bad Ruling’... bad and dirty Scientism!

Scientism is the dogmatic abuse of scientific prestige and religious fervor (rooted often in [faux]-Darwinian¹⁵ atheism) used to defend almost certainly immoral and unethical behaviors in the name of “The Science.”¹⁶ When, usually, the facts and empiricism run contrary to the claims of the Scientism¹⁷ adherents. In this way they are closer to Scientology than to the Scientific Method. However, while the cult of Scientology is honest about its desire for money and power, the cowards of the cults of Scientism, including the Peer Review Cult¹⁸ (PRC), and P.O.S.’s in general¹⁹, tend to make use of their a) position, b) prestige, c) Authority Fallacy, d) a priori

¹⁵ C. Darwin was, himself, a Christian.

¹⁶ <https://truthinscience.org/the-fallacy-of-follow-the-science/>

¹⁷ <https://sciencereigiondialogue.org/resources/what-is-scientism/>

¹⁸

https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

¹⁹ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

fallacy, e) pseudoscience (and it is particularly difficult to eradicate faux-hypotheses, f) reputation, g) access, and h) institutions of money, power, and governance to crush or eradicate their foes.

In this case, the desire of the Genetic Lobby for “fresh human/fetal tissue”²⁰ to be delivered to labs upon demand from abortion clinics²¹, is under threat from religious fundamentalism and from the Republic For Which We Stand, which gives **certain** enumerated and inalienable *God Given Rights (GGR)*²².

This is a problem and tension between the Scientism community, which typically has atheist or even Marxist-Leninist Atheist²³ leanings (MLA), or connections to outright Satanic Secret Societies^{24 25} (SSS). They do not like the human right to life²⁶. It interferes with the Genetic Lobby²⁷ and transhumanism²⁸ in general. Therefore, it’s a “threat to their freedom.”

However, the strongest push for the far leftists is probably not rooted in science at all, and most of the young women who get abortions are left **completely unaware** of how it will and does happen²⁹. Some imagine a scraping or a peaceful injection. In fact the practice is, by definition, “Cruel and Unusual Punishment”

*“In a nutshell, the cruel and unusual punishment clause measures a particular punishment against society’s prohibition against **inhumane treatment**. It prevents the government from imposing a penalty that is either barbaric or far too severe for the crime committed.”³⁰*

The penalty: fighting the odds to be born.

The punishment in abortion: vivisection (while alive), destruction by suction (a nearly Holocaustian attack on the person of the baby), and there are even attempts to allow the child to be born and then be murdered.^{31 32 33 34 35}

There are survivors, and they live with the damage done to their body, and no rights of remuneration for it. (See figures below)

²⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/528178a>

²¹ <https://www.crisismagazine.com/2021/fighting-the-fetal-tissue-research-industry-with-dr-stacy-trasancos>

²² <https://fee.org/articles/john-locke-natural-rights-to-life-liberty-and-property/>

²³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marxist%E2%80%93Leninist_atheism

²⁴ <https://www.exposingsatanism.org/secret-societies-pushing-for-a-one-world-religion/>

²⁵ <https://www.amazon.com/Illuminati-Facts-Fiction-Mark-Dice/dp/0967346657>

²⁶ See my book, “To Loot a Burning House” chapter on the New Cold War

<https://www.amazon.com/Loot-Burning-House-Ramon-Careaga/dp/1643384368>

²⁷ <https://www.opensecrets.org/Lobby/clientsum.php?id=F321197&year=2022>

²⁸ <https://www.hli.org/resources/what-is-transhumanism/>

²⁹ <https://www.liveaction.org/news/minds-change-abortion-right-life/> &

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WzfgTbrGzpm&feature=youtu.be>

³⁰ <https://www.nolo.com/legal-encyclopedia/the-meaning-cruel-unusual-punishment.html>

³¹ <https://jme.bmj.com/content/39/5/261>

³²

<https://cnsnews.com/news/article/emily-ward/virginia-governor-describes-how-post-birth-abortion-would-proceed>

³³ <https://www.independentsentinel.com/colorado-law-allows-post-birth-abortion-infanticide-up-to-28-days/>

³⁴

www.lifenews.com/2022/04/08/california-democrats-push-bill-to-legalize-infanticide-for-28-days-after-birth/

³⁵

<https://thefederalist.com/2022/04/12/california-bill-openly-admits-abortion-was-always-about-killing-babies>

Figure 1 - Abortion survivors; see: Abortion Survivor Network; credit: author/Google images

Let me be clear, this is **the only Libertarian picture** of the situation:

Figure 2 - Biological clarity of legal situation, and etymological origins of meaning of **Human**; credit: author

The fact that the human baby will either have a Y chromosome or not have one, (hence only two genders), is not relevant to *this* paper. But in a separate P.O.S. paper it may be necessary to lay out the why of the attack of 3rd and 4th wave feminism (and its Marxist ‘critical theory’ and anti-Scientific origins) on 2nd wave feminism (a nascent and patriotic, natural rights movement that led to the Gender Equal Pay Act (1963)³⁶, and for which Roe v Wade (1973)³⁷ is falsely synonymous with). However, that is not this paper. It may interest the reader, though, to know that “Roe” herself became Pro-Life³⁸. Or was she?^{39 40 41}

The Human Flesh Industry’s Gluttony for Fetus Cells

There is a longer paper to be written on this issue and slavery in general, to expose the pedophilic elite. However, in a nutshell, the Scientism lobby has spent a lot of money to prop up the genetic and abortion industries for the purposes of untold scientific and stem cell research. Firstly, the use of cadavers was considered basically worthless, as the dead body should have basically no living stem cells⁴². By their nature, stem cells⁴³ are nascent to the infantile and juvenile, and not to adults. Secondly, dead children are carefully guarded from science’s cold hands by parents and families.

This creates a unique Supply and Demand market issue for which the abortion industry finds itself in a particular niche, and for which they are willing to pay top dollar to lobbyists and propagandists (like the ACLU, SPLC, etc.) to continue to lie about the science of abortion, up to and including its procedure⁴⁴. To be clear, both sides do some lying. But if lying to spare lives is P.O.S. behavior and not a desperate attempt to save innocent babies, someone will need to put together that proof and show it to me! I’d like to see the mental gymnastics. I’m not talking about abortion clinic bombers⁴⁵ and the like. Just people who make up things about the abortion industry, which are frankly unneeded. The bare facts are horrific and genocidal enough (see the Appendix for what types of P.O.S. the fake-Libertarians and Independents are defending when they parrot the lies of the Left and extreme Left) without needing to lie or resort to “Bible Thumping.”

Thumping the Bible is a poor tactic at any rate, because most of these people don’t believe in God, a soul, the human spirit, and if there was a soul (to them) they’d probably sell it for tickets to Amy Schumer. They are “a wretched hive of scum and villainy” to be sure, but in

³⁶ <https://www.eeoc.gov/statutes/equal-pay-act-1963>

³⁷ <https://www.law.cornell.edu/supremecourt/text/410/113>

³⁸

<https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/soloish/wp/2016/01/22/the-fascinating-life-of-norma-mccorvey-the-jane-roe-in-roe-v-wade/>

³⁹ <https://time.com/6128139/roe-wade-daughter-abortion/>

⁴⁰ <https://newrepublic.com/article/163908/norma-mccorvey-roe-wade-switched-sides-abortion>

⁴¹

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-10779869/How-Jane-Roe-loathed-sides-daughter-tried-abort-writes-GUY-ADAMS.html>

⁴² Apparently they now find them in dead human brains

<https://www.livescience.com/20897-living-stem-cells-discovered-human-corpse.html>

⁴³ <https://www.explorestemcells.co.uk/AdultVSEmbryonicStemCells.html>

⁴⁴ <https://www.catholicworldreport.com/2017/07/26/poverty-is-not-the-root-cause-of-abortion/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2015/11/29/us/30abortion-clinic-violence.html>

the end synopsis, there is a right to be such. We shouldn't advocate for the end of free speech, these people do the best job of converting young women to the right side of Life when they make posts about roasting babies or killing all the white ones, etc. In the Appendix, we will be sure to showcase one of the top P.O.S. in this regard.

Figures 3 and 4 - CNN hosts these images, ironically, which show women of the Left/pro-Choice screeching at women on the right/Pro-Life in a vain effort to shut them up; credit: CNN⁴⁶

By the way, these women are also the victims of propaganda of socialism. Like fish they swim in it, blissfully (actually, quite angrily) unaware of it as their water. If they could stop quite-literally screeching for a moment and analyse the facts, or hear from those who survived abortions⁴⁷, most of them would moderate and adapt or completely change their beliefs (as Roe did). However, for that to happen, the limbic system⁴⁸ has to shut off and the cortex to rationally move through the ignorance of:

- Confirmation bias
- Dunning-Kruger
- Cognitive Dissonance
- Natural (but generally unacceptable) discrimination based on race⁴⁹ and/or sex (i.e. the "white male" thing... since much of the Pro-Life movement is led, vehemently, by women and mothers, which are a real thing no matter what political correctness delusions exist today)

⁴⁶ LOL: look at the actor 'male' on the left of shot:
<https://dynaimage.cdn.cnn.com/cnn/digital-images/org/c42817df-3e86-42f1-9f3d-df7377b1737f.jpg> "How did my life get here? Why did I become an FBI agent?"

⁴⁷ <https://video.foxnews.com/v/6000799340001#sp=show-clips>

⁴⁸

<https://www.encyclopedia.com/medicine/anatomy-and-physiology/anatomy-and-physiology/limbic-system>

⁴⁹ <https://phys.org/pdf10852.pdf>

Muh False “Property Rights” Trope

There is some [relatively] serious tension and reasoning behind a debate within Libertarians, the so-called Left-leaning (fake) vs. Classical Liberal or even Right-leaning (newcomers from Republicanism more rightly called paleo-conservatives⁵⁰) about the main purpose of Libertarianism. To be clear, property rights **are central**, as in core, to Libertarianism. However, they are not the end all and above all. They flow from GGR/natural rights (‘certain rights’), which means from religious authority⁵¹, as John Locke derived his “life, liberty and property”⁵² from his particular *liberal* (i.e. freedom from monarchy and Catholicism; see: Roman) position and understanding of God and Nature. God was not Nature, but made Nature and made mankind to be sovereign among Nature (see: Genesis, Daniel). Nevertheless, that to be naturally free as one is born (and eventually escape one’s parents in due time as an adult under the law; i.e. having left their home and lordship) one needs property (and by extension privacy, although not spelled out as such but as various privacy and ‘secured person’) rights.

This is the legal definition of property:

“n. anything that is owned by a person or entity. Property is divided into two types: “real property” which is any interest in land, real estate, growing plants or the improvements on it, and “personal property” (sometimes called “personalty”) which is everything else. “Common property” is ownership by more than one person of the same possession. “Community property” is a form of joint ownership between husband and wife recognized in several states. “Separate property” is property owned by one spouse only in a community property state, or a married woman’s sole ownership in some states. “Public property,” refers to ownership by a governmental body such as the federal, state, county or city governments or their agencies (e.g. school or redevelopment districts). The government, and, in particular, the courts are obligated to protect property rights and to help clarify ownership.”⁵³ (sic)

Therefore, the definition of property does not belong to one’s body, for if it did, and this would bother pro-Choicers, it’d be common property. I.e. a co-rental of space and habitation. Humans are not property, legally speaking. Bodies are also not property.

Muh False “My Body Autonomy” trope

Actually, you do not have a right to *do whatever* you wish with your body. These are some of the ways your body rights are limited, either by bad law, or for Clear and Present Danger reasons:

- Suicide
- Flashing or inappropriate exposure

⁵⁰ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/paleoconservative>

⁵¹ <https://iep.utm.edu/locke-et/>

⁵²

<https://oll.libertyfund.org/quote/john-locke-on-the-rights-to-life-liberty-and-property-of-ourselves-and-others-1689>

⁵³ <https://legal-dictionary.thefreedictionary.com/property>

- Public waste elimination
- Drug Use
- Transportation
- Draft / military service
- Jail for criminal suspicion
- Prison for criminal prosecution
- Capture for felony fugitive status (eg. by a bondsman or bounty hunter)

*Note that refusing a vaccination is considered by SCOTUS as completely fine under religious exemption, and otherwise any forced vaccination would need to show that failure to do so constitutes a **Clear and Present Danger** to the public and specific persons. Ebola would be an example of a very CaPD pathogen, whereas HIV or COVID would not. Definitely the latter⁵⁴.

Muh False “Clump of Cells” trope

There is a weird sophistry attempted on the Left in general, and it reflects Scientism as well, to attempt to replace words. So a baby becomes a mere fetus. Later that fetus becomes a mere clump of cells. And how can a clump of cells be considered a human let alone a person? Three or four degrees of separation are what give them false moral authority to determine the fetus is really *better off dead* and the mother’s life freer for it. Actually, no one is free from sin, but setting the religious aside, we can see this trope falls apart with two immediate facts:

- ❖ Life begins at conception
 - So birth control needs to work before this to not be homicide
- ❖ A DNA test will **always** prove the zygote, fetus, baby etc. to be a human
 - See definition and etymology of homicide and human

Figure 5 - u/Warlocke (probably a Libertarian reference) insane post with sophistry to rationalize killing orphans; credit: Twitter/Reddit Lies⁵⁵

This is pretty inconvenient, and they know this. Therefore the discussion has shifted, thanks to the convenient gift of

⁵⁴ <https://news.cornell.edu/stories/2020/04/why-covid-19-mild-some-deadly-others>

⁵⁵ https://twitter.com/reddit_lies/status/1522035778955714560

neuroscientists, to the idea of consciousness and the formation of the brain.

However, the Theory of Mind⁵⁶ has shown that a) the Mind never stops developing or changing, and b) is related to but not constrained by complexity and nerve centers.

For starters, there are now **five** known loci of nerve centers in the body, leaving the neocortex as a singular one:

1. Upper CNS
2. Cerebellum and Medulla/Pons
3. Lower CNS (i.e. the so called reptilian brain)
4. The PNS (including genital consciousness, eg. 'female intuition')
5. The ENS (i.e. the mesentery organ, eg. 'gut feeling')

This isn't to be pedantic and begin dividing the brain. It's enough to say these five reflect the five phases, as well as diversity of bodily agenda. Nevertheless, they also **develop at different rates within the stages in utero.**

They **all** feel pain.

Muh False "Women's Rights" (under attack) trope

Women's rights is not a constitutional thing but a social convention to describe the egalitarian effort, quite humanistic, in not treating women any longer as property, as under Sharia⁵⁷, or Communism, or Monarchism, etc. A tribe doesn't own its people, to be sure, neither do the individuals have rights. That's why this isn't a "tribal Republic." Let us, for one second, look at what tribes of Native America used to do to women, men and babies⁵⁸:

- *"To gasps of horror from the watching crowds, the Indians presented her at the Council House in the ranching town of San Antonio in 1840, the year Queen Victoria married Prince Albert. 'Her head, arms and face were full of bruises and sores,' wrote one witness, Mary Maverick. 'And her nose was actually burnt off to the bone. Both nostrils were wide open and denuded of flesh.' Once handed over, Matilda Lockhart broke down as she described the horrors she had endured — the rape, the relentless sexual humiliation and the way Comanche women had tortured her with fire. It wasn't just her nose, her thin body was hideously scarred all over with burns. When she mentioned she thought there were 15 other white captives at the Indians' camp, all of them being subjected to a similar fate, the Texan lawmakers and officials said they were detaining the Comanche chiefs while they rescued the others."*⁵⁹
- *"This is quoted from a theses dissertation by Adam Stuecke, titled "A Place Under Heaven: Amerindian Torture and Cultural Violence in Colonial New France, 1609-1729". You can find it online.*⁶⁰

⁵⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/psychology/theory-of-mind>

⁵⁷ A far-right institution;

<https://nypost.com/2016/04/06/there-are-muslim-men-fighting-for-the-right-to-kill-their-wives/>

⁵⁸ It is presumed by the author they would exact revenge for the deaths of their own pregnant women at the hands of enemy tribes.

⁵⁹

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2396760/How-Comanche-Indians-butchered-babies-roasted-ene-mies-alive.html>

⁶⁰ https://epublications.marquette.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1174&context=dissertations_mu

In this chapter, the author describes and explains the tortures inflicted upon an Iroquois prisoner, Saunadanoncoua, by the now vanished Hurons.

The scholar gives some interesting perspectives on the cultural context, but notwithstanding the culture and reasoning behind these deeds, these tortures remain atrocious.

“The Hurons burned Saunadanoncoua upon the legs with firebrands as he ran about the building. When he shrieked in pain, the crowd repeated his shrieks. When he became tired of running and stopped at one end of the building, the Hurons crushed the bones in his hands, pierced his ears with sticks, and bound his wrists so tightly they further crushed his hands. When Saunadanoncoua needed to rest, the Hurons allowed him to do so, but forced him to sit on piles of hot ash and smoldering coals. When he stated he was unable to rise from the ash pile, the Hurons thrust a fire brand upon his groin and he fainted. At this point the Hurons stopped for fear that if it went any further, Saunadanoncoua would die too soon, before “he should see the daytime.”

The Hurons shifted from a mood of humanity and admiration for Saunadanoncoua to relentless torture with incredible speed. This was a controlled use of pain, as is evident in the special attention the Hurons paid to his already wounded hands. The Hurons understood how they could inflict the most pain with the least chance of death, and pursued this quite systematically. Also, with a simple order to stop, all those participating did so and this is further evidence that this was a controlled and planned out act, and not the orgy of violence it appears to be at first sight.

The Hurons revived Saunadanoncoua, allowed him to drink some water, and then commanded him to sing. At first he did so in a very weak voice, but he quickly rose up and sang with a fervor that the Jesuit observers thought to be near superhuman. After Saunadanoncoua fainted, the Hurons had filed out, but rushed back in when he began to sing. The Hurons took the cords that bound his hands and set them on fire, they rubbed out fire brands into his legs, and they pressed heated hatchet blades to his feet.

It was at this point that a verbal exchange began between the Hurons and Saunadanoncoua, as the Hurons filled their language with metaphor and dualistic imagery that helped all involved to build towards a focal point. This exchange reveals the most about the dynamic created between the two factions at this specific place and time in which both groups utilized their emotional and intellectual selves against each other. A Huron said to Saunadanoncoua: “Come... let me talk and pitch my canoe, it is a beautiful canoe which I lately traded for; I must stop all the water holes in it.” He said this even as he ran a fire brand slowly up and down Saunadanoncoua’s legs. This Huron used aesthetic irony and dualistic language to alter the use of the word beautiful, beyond the traditional meaning to include the violent spectacle of Saunadanoncoua. This use of dualistic language goes beyond the act of torture though. He stated that he recently “traded” for his canoe. This could be a play on words to interchange “trade” for “capture.” This could also be a reference to the dead nephew of Saudanuscouay, for whom Saunadanoncoua took the place of through torture. The torture is a dualistic gesture of love for Sauandauscouay’s nephew, and aggression towards the Iroquois who killed him via the conduit of Saunadanoncoua. This is also the reason the Hurons began to refer to him as uncle.

Next came the most revealing example of the dualistic relationship between the captors and the captive, and both the verbal and non-verbal communication between the two as the captors worked to maintain control of their emotional selves and the captive worked to maintain the link to his intellectual self. This occurred when a Huron said to Saunadanoncoua: "Come uncle, where do you prefer that I should burn you?" Father Le Mercier specifically stated that Saunadanoncoua then pointed to a place on his body where he should be burned next.

With a single motion of a burned, mangled hand, Saunadanoncoua sent a clear message to his Huron captors that as he lingered somewhere between life and death, he maintained control of his intellectual self. This was the underlying reason they continued to ask as they pursued the group goal of distinguishing themselves as the controllers of both themselves and the situation. By maintaining his ability to answer their questions, Saunadanoncoua proved his own self control. With each passing moment towards dawn and his inevitable death, he increased his control of the situation as they failed to render him insensible and insured that his emotional soul would remain near his body and potentially plague them at a later point. "For my part, I do not know anything about burning," one said as he burned Saunadanoncoua. Another commented: "Ah, it is not right that my uncle should be cold: I must warm thee." Another placed a pair of stockings on his legs and then set them on fire. They continued to ask Saunadanoncoua: "And now, uncle, hast thou had enough?" When he replied that he indeed had enough the Hurons only replied: "No, it is not enough," and they continued to burn him.

It would be easy to view these exchanges as sadistic abuse on the part of the Hurons, but it must be kept in mind that within the intricate nature of Amerindian oratory and religious belief, it was a rhetorical question. If Saunadanoncoua could answer the question at all, it was not enough. He needed to be rendered senseless for the torture to be successful. Even to answer that he had had enough was a message that he still controlled both his mind and body. All he needed to do to end his torture was to lose his faculties and surrender to the immeasurable pain he had endured for hours, yet he did not. The Hurons continued throughout the night until it became clear that if they continued, Saunadanoncoua would die before daybreak.

They gave Saunadanoncoua food and water and let him rest while they conversed with him and the Jesuits. They talked about several subjects, including French methods of torture and execution and the nature of Heaven and Hell. The Hurons questioned Saunadanoncoua about the state of affairs in Iroquoia, and if he knew the fate of several Hurons recently taken captive. He openly volunteered information about Iroquoia and apparently knew of several Hurons killed in battle and taken captive. The Jesuits were impressed by the coherence of his thought and speech during this conversation. "He did this as easily, and with a countenance as composed, as any one there present would have showed." He in fact thanked the Hurons for taking the time to talk with him, and stated that it had temporarily: "diverted him from his troubles." When the sun rose, the Hurons brought Saunadanoncoua outside and kindled fresh fires.

Here the process of torture took on a new level of complexity. As quickly and easily as the Hurons burned and tortured Saunadanoncoua, they just as quickly calmed once again and conversed with him almost as if he were an adoptee, or even a visitor. This

was a deliberate display of control over their emotional selves. Saunadanoncoua clearly took this as an opportunity to manipulate both the Jesuits and Hurons by first distracting them with information on their absent tribesmen and an interest in Catholic dogma. In the process, they allowed Saunadanoncoua an opportunity to regain his composure and illustrate his own control over his intellectual self. He also took the opportunity to again show off his oratory skills with the subtle insult of referring to their skill as torturers as his “troubles.”

The goal of the Hurons was to burn this man to the point of death, and force him into pain induced hysteria. They allowed themselves to be manipulated into doing just the opposite when they helped Saunadanoncoua forget his pain for a few minutes. It was through the manipulation of this pain that both captor and captive fought this conflict. The Hurons proved unable to render Saunadanoncoua insensible, and in these final stages of torture before dawn, he forced them to either allow him to rest and reaffirm his own self-control, or to allow him to die and open themselves to greater risks from his sken.

The lesser of these two risks was to allow him a rest and to keep him alive. At day break the Hurons brought Saunadanoncoua outside and placed him upon a platform about six feet high. Three or four Huron mounted the platform with him and as the sun rose, they burned him without regard for his life. They forced firebrands down his throat and into his anus. They burned out his eyes and placed a necklace of heated hatchet blades around his neck. They poured water down his throat and upon seeing that he was motionless, they cut off first a foot, then his hand, and finally his head, which they threw into the crowd. Later, they gave it to Ondessone who ate it. The other Hurons ate most of Saunadanoncoua’s remains at a feast later that day.”⁶¹

- True accounts of how women were treated by tribes is also pretty gruesome. See the account of Jenny Wiley’s escape⁶² and many others.

This isn’t to say that it was only hard because of tribalism. In general life before the Enlightenment began freeing women, mostly with industrialization, plumbing and white-male-invented women’s hygiene products^{63 64} was pretty rough. Look at what one source says about birth control in the 1800’s:

“1800’s Birth Control

Life was hard on the frontier, especially for women. According to the 1850 U.S. census, the first ever conducted nationwide, the average woman had six children, down from 7-8 in 1800. Pregnancy and childbirth were major killers of women and in the western frontier, the mortality rate was three times higher than in New England and more than 50 times what it is today. (Imagine giving birth in a Conestoga wagon on the rutted and rocky Oregon Trail!)

That wasn’t the only problem. After the Civil War, the 2.75 million soldiers coming home from the war suffered from epidemic rates of alcoholism and opiate addiction. (See

⁶¹ <https://www.quora.com/What-were-the-worst-tortures-performed-by-Native-Americans?share=1>

⁶² <https://nativeheritageproject.com/2014/04/30/jenny-wiley-captive-white-woman/>

⁶³ <https://www.thetalko.com/15-womens-products-that-are-simply-life-saving-and-are-invented-by-men/>

⁶⁴ <https://menstrualcup.co/history-of-feminine-hygiene-products/>

previous post, "Cocaine Candy in the Old West"). Unemployment, PTSD (called "soldier's heart" in the 1860s), and domestic violence were at epidemic rates as well.

Women were desperate to control the number of children they had and there was a voracious market for birth control methods. This, despite the fact that in the 1840s, state legislatures began passing laws outlawing the sale and use of contraceptives until the 1873 Comstock Law banned them federally. By 1880, abortion, too, was criminalized in all states.

By 1850, contraceptive products were massively marketed and advertised in ladies magazines as "female pills," "Mother's friend," "prevention powders," and "regulator tablets." Tablets or tinctures of pennyroyal, rue, foxglove, angelica root, or partridge berry, marketed as "squaw vine," worked in various ways as abortifacients or preventives.

Condoms and crude diaphragms and precursors to the IUD were also invented and on the market by the 1850s. Charles Goodyear's 1839 rubber "vulcanization" process revolutionized condom manufacturing. Birth control douches became popular, as well. All sort of concoctions, some deadly, were used, including bleach, sulfate of zinc, and, starting in the 1880s, Coca Cola and Lysol!

The many forms of birth control of the 1800s varied wildly in their ineffectiveness and many were deadly or left women damaged for life. Despite the dangers, the fertility rate of the nation's female population continued to plummet consistently for the entire 19th century.

Native American women, too, used birth control methods. They were not only empowered by cultural knowledge passed down through generations, but by a natural pharmacopeia of plants and herbs available to them in nature. The Hopi and Tewa used the Indian paintbrush plant to prevent pregnancy and the Navajo, stoneseed. Tea made from false hellebore root was used by both women and men to prevent children in the Paiute, Washo, and Shoshone tribes. The Shoshone also used stoneseed and one-seed juniper berries. Tea from bitter cherry wood was used by the Skokomish, Skagit, Lummi, and Quinalt. Blue cohosh was perhaps the most commonly used among many tribes as an abortifacient, as well as to induce labor.⁶⁵

The point is *if* the Founding Fathers left out 'women's rights' it isn't because they were men (only). They were trying to create a *more perfect union* which was always improving. That culminated with the Gender Equal Pay Act of 1974, and now we are well past parity. Men have virtually no spaces belonging solely to them⁶⁶, and women have more of everything than ever... and still are not, statistically speaking⁶⁷, happy. Men have invented almost everything⁶⁸, with the exceptions of some unique and amazing women, including forgotten (due to sexism from both

⁶⁵ There are photos of abortion and contraceptive devices on site <https://www.notesfromthefrontier.com/post/1800s-birth-control>

⁶⁶ The NFL is primarily made up of men; and yet there is always a pink/breast Cancer awareness week or month, etc. You do not see that reciprocation about prostate cancer *anywhere*. This is a small example of the double standards in our society. Multiple social experiments show people don't care about violence against men.

⁶⁷ <https://www.theguardian.com/lifeandstyle/2016/may/18/womens-rights-happiness-wellbeing-gender-gap>

⁶⁸ It is well over 99%

sexes) scientists⁶⁹, even quantum physicists⁷⁰! However, *in the case of homicide*, **none of this social morasse is relevant.**

- ★ All that is relevant is that the individual is the greatest minority needing of protection from tyranny; and no group deserves special rights to deal out punishment and death; or all do⁷¹.

Muh False “Men Need to Shut Up” trope

If the discussion, also involving “women’s rights” such as rape (not that all victims of rape are women or girls) were to be had, no one would say “men need to shut up.” They’d say “listen” and “understand,” but they’d want confirmation that men understood the issue from the female perspective. Similarly, it takes a male and female to make a child/offspring. There are myriad times we wouldn’t say “women need to shut up” (even if we should, it wouldn’t be prudent or acceptable). Therefore, this trope has no legs to stand on. Or rather, it’s an idea that doesn’t hold water, just by alternating the point of view. A sure sign of a shallow argument.⁷²

Muh False “Republicans hate women” trope

One of the more irkesome tropes, for a variety of reasons, is the idea that white/male/cis/Chrstian/Republicans are out to hurt women, take their rights, and enslave them in the *punishment* of motherhood.

What a bunch of fking bologna.**

⁶⁹ <http://www.nature.com/scitable/topicpage/rosalind-franklin-a-crucial-contribution-6538012>

⁷⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hendrika_Johanna_van_Leeuwen

⁷¹ And that is a Native American tribal belief, though they had limits. You had to exact your revenge within one year or forego it under common law of “the People”. The ‘defendant’ against revenge might as well flee to join another tribe and await that day. Like as not women could also get revenge, not only in Native America, but Europe, Africa, Asia, etc. And the entire world was and is racist. Back then people were racist against even others of their own color! Anti-semitism against white jews is still commonplace among white protestants.

⁷² Isn’t it funny, though, that as soon as the memo was leaked, that “pregnant persons” disappeared and women reappeared (to the Left), they figured out how fertility works, and suddenly trans women were no longer pertinent? Suddenly the emotions of the argument zeroed in very quickly on a definition (XX) of woman and mother. Funny how that happens.

Some of the more prominent figures of the pro-Life movement are not only women⁷³, some of them are atheists (with Libertarian ethical leanings). Moreover, there is nothing wrong with motherhood or even being a stay-at-home mother⁷⁴. There is something mentally wrong with people who treat abortion as a 'good' thing. I have treated mothers who had abortions, and none of them were in celebration. Some have spent their adult lives in regret and repentance. It is a tragedy for all sides. Even when it is a self-defense, the situation is rape, incest, or disease, what-have-you, it is a tragedy. This cancer culture of celebration of murder and death, wrapped in a veneer of female empowerment leads young girls down a primrose path of self-abnegation and virtual moral destruction of their character. They will often laud individuals that say the most vile and reprehensible (and nonsensical) things... and this has been falsely and disgustingly transferred into the Libertarian ethos via the idea of Freedom (of expression mostly, but of fake women's rights as well). This is a serious problem, and it is fostered by the Party of Systemic Racism: the Democrat Party. It's propaganda, once again, and it's an example of how Lincoln's Civil War never ended. And also why it was probably a bad idea to begin with. People have to want to change. Democrats have to stop wanting to own minorities (particularly black minds) and women, if they at all want peace, liberalism, or respect and historical correctness.. It isn't clear to me that the party has any JFK/FDR left in it at all. For that matter neither does the GOP, but that is a Bush family matter for another time (we have to discuss Nazis, Skull n Bones, and Leftism via NeoLiberalism). Right now, the charge that being Pro-Life or Pro-Cosntitution makes you a cis-white-male-Republican is a bit of a tired trope.

I am a straight-white-male but I'm a Christaoist (or Buddeo-Christian) Libertarian forced to vote anti-Democrat based on treason, 1984 Orwellianism, Endless War, Biden Crime Syndicate, etc. The point is I wasn't initially anti-Democrat,, and I was never Republican before the Socialist ((Agenda21/2030)) in 2019+! That is the Democrats' own fault, and the Libertarians who allowed themselves to be infiltrated with these false tropes. All my views, however, as you have seen, are rooted in factual history, definition, etymology, rationalism, and **not in Critical Theory Historical Revisionism**. They have nothing to do with the JFK-Democrat, President Donald Trump. Being a father, certainly. But more so, being a pro-rationalism, pro-Enlightenment and not Unlightenment values spiritual healer. Christian, Taoist, Buddhist... they all share a respect for the sanctity of human life. So does Islam, to a degree. They all have hypocrites. But they all have standards and standard-bearers. Scientism is a false religion, and its adherents make a mockery of Truth because they ignore GGR, rationalism, and even empirical evidence.

Muh False "Fox News/Tucker Carlson/MAGA" trope

A newer behavior in the Libertarian landscape has been to conflate what we love to call Faux News (being aware of Rupert's war of Journalism and Truth) with Tucker the person with the "Trump Train" (called MAGA-ism), and identifying all of this with Pro-Lifers. It is true there is

⁷³ "If the draft opinion made public tonight is the final opinion of the court, we wholeheartedly applaud the decision," Marjorie Dannenfelser — the president of Susan B. Anthony List, which supports anti-abortion politicians — said in a statement Monday."

<https://www.cnn.com/politics/live-news/scotus-abortion-rights-reactions/index.html>

⁷⁴ Which Oprah called (falsely) the "hardest job in the world!" [LOL]

This comedian, a white man married to a black woman, deals with this most hilariously, by the way: ^

a sizable venn diagram overlap of these items. However, rationally speaking it's a non-sequitur as many of the "Q" variety of the Trump Train despise Fox News, distrust it, and it isn't clear if they are Pro-Lifers so much as anti-pederasts. Fun fact, all of the pederasts and LGBTQP+ pushes on Twitter were self-identified voters of Hillary Clinton in 2016, based on my deep dive into Pizzagate. However, quite a few Republicans who are more than typically Pro-Life actually hated Donald Trump. After he supported the Red Flag law, he lost a goodly number of the non-worshippers (of his ego) to Libertarianism.

Libertarians, conversely and strangely, defend Fox News' right to be a corporation (person or not is a hot topic of contention), but despise it nevertheless and prefer CNBC, BBC, NPR, etc. However, most will agree that Tucker does a decent job of exposing RINOs and Leftism in general, and most will concordantly agree CNN is also fake news. What that all means in terms of Pro-Life or not is diddly-squat.

What matters to most Libertarians, if they are indeed Libertarian and not transplants from the Green, Independent, or two main parties, is actually things like National Security, Property Rights, Economics, Limited Government, etc. Pro-Life is sadly not a common facet of that. But those who are staunch "body rightists" are also there, and if they are pro Fox News, then the Left has misunderstood the problem, immensely, as Libertarians see it!

Open Borders and Weak National Security are NOT Libertarian

Libertarianism isn't fundamentally a property rights platform, though that is core. It is a Bill of Rights and Limited Government platform. By extension most classical Libertarians are "fiscally conservative" and "socially liberal", meaning pro-sex education, pro-Marijuana rights, etc. There is nothing particularly socially liberal about a fake form of limited government such as Open Borders... it is just foolish with regard to National Security. NS is a euphemism for defending the land, and that's what Patriots do. Patriots in Americanism in general are anti-nationalistic, and pro-Federalistic. Meaning limit the government to these basic duties:

- Self-regulation
- Border and national defense (especially of the Union from attack)
- End monopolies and break up illegal trusts
- Protect or 'get out of the way' of Human Rights (i.e. Bill of Rights and other laws, like Miranda Rights)
- Regulate international (via tariffs) and interstate commerce (via taxation with representation)
- Tax only corporate income (and not wages, if someone would stop the IRS that'd be great!⁷⁵)
- Issue bonds and secure notes, secure finances of the Federal Government
 - Libertarians would prefer a balanced or profitable budget, and neither of the two parties do that, anymore.

⁷⁵ Voluntary my ass.

These issues cannot be handled properly if the government is overrun by various forms of invaders, *or concurrently* a collapse of the economy and/or birth rate precludes the formation of the “well regulated militias”⁷⁶ and the military (Marines, Army, Navy, etc.).

The following graph shows the alarming collapse of the National Birthrate during the Roe v Wade era, which only opened America up to the Socialist asymmetric attack further (and helped the Communists, of which many Pro-Choicers are ghastly and unabashedly adherents of):

Figure 7 - US fertility rates⁷⁷ (per woman) since 1800; rates were already declining at the time of Roe v Wade; but it had a massive and measurable impact. What most helped women have fewer child labors was industrialization. We are now below the replacement rate of 2.1

Furthermore, owing to the particular engineering (via evolution and not design) of capitalism, it has a growth rate issue. This is exacerbated especially by the inflationary issue of Keynesian economic theory which ran this country’s Federal Reserve Bank (private) system since Paleo-Liberalism of the 1930s began right through and more amok in Neoliberalism and Neoconservatism. The inflation **requires** debt and coverage of debt, and that isn’t going to happen if the population shrinks... hence “Great Reset” and “end the Fed” (not from Libertarians now, but NGO’s and foreign actors/enemies⁷⁸.) But even without the neoliberal “print to Heaven” behavior, capitalism as it exists now in corporate bonding, credit default swaps, collateralized

⁷⁶ See: 2nd Amendment

⁷⁷ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1033027/fertility-rate-us-1800-2020/>

⁷⁸ I.e. Chussia and Axis enemies. Including OPEC, etc.

debt obligations, stock and bond markets, etc. would collapse into recession at a below 2.5% growth rate.

To have that growth rate, you need home buyers. And to have those you need wage earners and entrepreneurs... which means **you need people**. Shrinkage of population is therefore the **most insidious direct threat to national security possible**. It is not an indirect threat, but a direct and obvious one. Open Borders is an indirect threat. Immigration is a Libertarian platform. But Open Borders defies the national security tenet of 'limited government', and therefore is not only anti-liberal (by diluting votes), but a national security threat. However, it pales, far in comparison, to the direct threat to national security posed by the immoral, unethical hazard of wanton, open, cheap and easy abortion.

Not the least of which, let us mention that of the 55 million deaths in America alone, some untold millions of soldiers, doctors, playwrights, teachers, firemen, policemen (and women), and workers including garbagemen, line-workers, engineers, concrete layers, electricians, plumbers, etc. that are vital to the social fabric and infrastructure of the great country were snuffed out because of the selfishness of their 55 million would-be mothers who had a lot of growing up to do. The pain for those mothers is more intense than anyone talks about. But the crime of the doctors, industry, and yes mothers against their countrymen is a treason far more grave than has ever been openly spoken of. It is, in fact, violations of the Geneva Conventions, of common sense, of rationalism, and of course a sin of epic and maybe irreversible proportions.

Conclusion

The real conclusion is below, but it is sufficient to say that herein a factual accounting of the real Libertarian position is found. We live in an age of fakery and substitutions, plastic bubbles and safe spaces. Naturally, it is to be expected the Libertarian Party (and its new adherents) would not be capable of understanding this). All explanations of how tribalism doesn't fix the issue any more than identity politics and the Left vs. Right battle, are purely to show the complexity of the issue, and why it is so important to rely on SCOTUS doctrine and the Constitution itself. In the end, much is about opinions, left, right, or center. But beyond the 'rainbow of gray' in this world of moral relativism, there is an absolute Right and Wrong, Good and Evil.

The SCOTUS' job is to adhere to the Constitution, as it is our founding document meant to keep us on the path of ultimate Good and away from ultimate Evil (like the Human Flesh Industry and baby murder). The future will look back on this time and this fight very unkindly towards those that made humanity's sanctified soul into trash to uphold a sacrilegious, Satanic passtime of the cataclysms and barbaric tribalistic past. They will, undoubtedly view pure homo sapiens without digital transhumanist elements as a rarity, like a Javan Tiger. And they will marvel that anyone would want to kill something that cannot speak yet or fight back, which is sentient. We may even, by then, discover the science of soul and spirit. How foolish will our culture and 'civilization' look then?

The caprice of a woman (or her pushy partner) to commit such a mistake in order to further her (or their) convenience is clearly wrong, on all levels. Again, excepting those situations which have Clear and Present Danger to the mother. There is no danger to having to adjust your life to raise a person that will love you more than you clearly deserve. Grow up.

POS Theory :: Opinion Editorial

Accept responsibility. And if you're Libertarian, stop making excuses for abuse of freedom. Freedom isn't free, and its price is eternal vigilance. Furthermore, it is never more than a generation away from disappearing. Guard it well.

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

Appendix - the P.O.S. display of Abortion Advocates

AKA, Why would any Libertarian want to be associated with these heinous and ugly people, given the noble goal of Libertarianism: “take over the world and leave you the Hell alone”? A noble, humanitarian and egalitarian pursuit of the highest equalities: true **Life, Liberty, and Pursuit of Happiness** (and Property).

‘Enjoy’ these most disgusting and now immortalized examples of the P.O.S. of the day, losing their minds in an attempt to harm the Republic by upsetting the balance of the Supreme Court of the United States.

P.O.S. Supremes

Baby Roaster Lady @liveactionorg ⁷⁹

liveactionorg Live Action · 4-7

We want answers. #JusticeForTheFive #washingtondc #curtisbayenergy #abortion #criminal #newstiktok
🎵 original sound - noah

Any discussion of roasting babies, aborted or not, to create electricity is inherent P.O.S. Supreme behavior. The fact that this was liked by 31.5k people (as of this writing) on a platform controlled by the Chinese Communist Party is just incredibly academic. Whole studies could be done about what is happening here.

⁷⁹

https://www.tiktok.com/foryou?feed_mode=v1&is_from_webapp=v1&item_id=7083979454090923306#@liveactionorg/video/7083979454090923306

Amanda Duarte

 Amanda Duar... @duarteaman... · 47m ...
Please know that I am deeply, deeply sorry, and if there is anything I can do to repair the damage of this, please do let me know. Thank you.

282 25 33

[Show this thread](#)

 Amanda Duar... @duarteaman... · 47m ...
I deleted my account briefly because I wasn't sure of the right thing to do, and I knew that it wasn't and isn't to try to answer for what I said. I know a lot of people are angry and looking to tell me why, so I'm reactivating it because I think that is important.

65 19 23

[Show this thread](#)

 Amanda Duar... @duarteaman... · 47m ...
I said something insanely awful and stupid on twitter last night. The intent does not matter so I will not attempt to defend or explain it. It was racist and has had racist impact. I am terribly sorry to anyone and everyone who read it, and who were hurt by it.

661 159 56

 Amanda Duarte @duarteamanda ...
I do wonder how these white supremacist lawmakers would feel if their little white daughters were raped and impregnated by black men.

22:18 · 2022-05-02 · [Twitter for iPhone](#)

27 Quote Tweets 6 Likes

This Tweet has been deleted.

 Amanda Duarte @duarteamanda 11/19/21
Please stop having white children

 Amanda Duarte @duarteamanda 4/7/22
perhaps the hardest truth of all to accept must be that no one wants to fuck your disgusting little white kids

 Amanda Duarte @duarteamanda 3/25/22
Friends, THE ENTIRE ANTI-ABORTION MOVEMENT IS ABOUT WHITE SUPREMACY. More white women have abortions than any other group and they need those babies to grow up and be trained to be racist voters or they're gone.

[Show this thread](#)

Honestly, is anyone shocked at this point that the Left is so blatantly sexist and racist?

“Motherboard”

Holy Double-Think Batman! Just imagine being capable of attacking someone for taking something made for humans prescribed by their doctor, **then hypocritically wanting people to hurt themselves in order to murder babies** by taking medication literally made for horses.

Leann (@diaryofabluedot)

Hard to describe this one. So I'll transcribe what she said, and you can click on her link⁸⁰ if you want to see what type of toxic factory of insanity/inanity this woman (+demon) produces.

*“Here’s the thing. It doesn’t matter when life begins. It doesn’t matter whether a fetus is a human being or not, that argument is a red herring, a distraction, a subjective and unwinnable argument that could not matter less. It doesn’t matter whether we’re talking about a fertilized egg, or a fetus, **or a baby, or a 5 year old, or a Nobel-prize winning pediatric oncologist...**”*

It continues in this vain, inane manner about pointless discussion of the body's autonomy (which doesn't exist). Let's just focus on what she said. She's saying murder is ok, so long as anyone wants to "use" her body. Babies don't use the mother. They are symbiotic, period. She is a clinically insane wreck of a human. And she needs to be called out.

⁸⁰ <https://www.tiktok.com/@diaryofabluedot>

Simon Gwynn (@SimonGwynn)

This is a certain kind of low character P.O.S. that I really despise, even more than hyperbolic (completely weak and fake) burn the babies girl. This person uses their following to help create a situation like doxxing the Conservative Supreme Court Justices⁸¹, and then expects to get away with it by “walking it back” because “it was a thought experiment” (and not what it actually is: a dog whistle for overt violence against a very specific person or set of persons, which is highly illegal and not free speech).

81

<https://conservativemodern.com/leftwing-group-doxxes-home-address-of-conservative-supreme-court-justices/>

P.O.S. Light

These are examples of fairly reprehensible Social Media posts, not as extreme. Again, this isn't a mere political difference of opinion. And let me be clear, all of these Appendix examples are something I support the freedom to say. Because I'd like to see the modern P.O.S. (like yesteryear's KKK/Democrat or the modern far-right Neo-Nazi, or the black supremacist "Black Hebrew Israelites, etc.) out in front where they can be identified.

Yvette Brown

Blaming Trump (so called Trump Derangement Syndrome) for SCOTUS finally doing its job is bad enough; calling the 45th President, a man who got two landmark peace deals done and highly funded Historically black Colleges as well as pardoned posthumously Jack Johnson, a racist is really ignorant P.O.S. behavior.

Chris Evans

There is a special place in Non-Sequitur Hell for this type of post.

 steven
@egyptian_neenan

The @GOP hates women and is sentencing an entire generation to death. #RoeVWade

apple.news
Exclusive: Supreme Court has voted to overturn abortion rights, ...
"We hold that Roe and Casey must be overruled," Justice Alito writes in an initial majority draft circulated inside the court.

8:42 PM · May 2, 2022

3.8K Reply Share

[Read 686 replies](#)

Steven Neenan

Holy Double-Speak Batman!
Next up in Orwellianism, and a continuation of the lies about anti-vaccination mandaters⁸², is the idea that not killing **is killing**.

Again that 3,800 people (as of this writing) liked this post, is a real study in the toxicity of Social Media.

cutekittensmeow ↑ 708 🏆 1 10h

Fuck all this nonsense. I'm pro-abortion. I'm pro-destroying fetuses. There should be MORE abortions because abortions are normal.

I'm pro-abortion because a woman doesn't need a reason to have an abortion.

I had an abortion because I just didn't want a kid. Period. I wasn't raped, I was totally healthy, I had a loving relationship, I had plenty of money. I had unprotected sex with my boyfriend because it felt good and I got pregnant. I didn't want a kid so I had an abortion.

u/cutekittensmeow⁸³

Aka "I just want to kill and have no repercussions for poor sexual choices."

Aka "I'm a murderer unrepentant"

Aka "At least this one is being honest about 99% of the circumstances..."

12:30 PM · May 5, 2022 · Twitter for iPhone

⁸² Some of which are Libertarians, but not all.

⁸³ https://twitter.com/reddit_lies/status/1522252323275395074

Jim Obergefell⁸⁴

"The extreme U.S. Supreme Court should not be overturning decades of established law and denying the most basic human health rights to pregnant people to make their own decisions about their lives and their bodies," the statement read. "The sad part is ... five or six people will determine the law of the land and go against the vast majority of Americans who overwhelmingly support a person's right to make their own health decisions and a couple's right to be married."⁸⁵ This is a sad day, but it's not over. We have fought the good fight for too long to be denied our rights now."

Let me be clear, his P.O.S. status is for lying, shoe-horning, and grandstanding, not his sexuality (or even his use of his dead husband as a prop in an issue completely, and definitely unrelated to gay marriage).

The court isn't extreme. The decades of established law comparison is like comparing Plessy v. Ferguson to Brown v. Board... And who is the "we" in this fight for rights? This is an inherently identitarian and political statement, and not based on anything rational. Finally it was five **men** that decided (wrongly) on Roe v Wade, and it was always a well known poor ruling along party lines rather than Constitutional Law. It was judicial activism at the highest level. It isn't about what democracy thinks. Democracy is two wolves and a sheep deciding who is for dinner. (See Baby Roaster lady and SoyLent Green jokes write themselves.) It is about protecting the rights of a minority: the ones who cannot fight back or speak for themselves... **Future Americans**. No matter their color, creed, sex, or other immutable characteristics. Abortion isn't a health right. It is a genocide of black people that morphed into an out of control industry fueled by hype, money, stem cell research, and propaganda. This has **nothing whatsoever** to do with "gay rights" or homosexual anything.

The right to regulate homicide belongs to the state. You like murdering babies? Move to a state that makes it a misdemeanor or less. Enjoy the crime, disease, poverty, racism, and destruction of private property that comes with that choice. *"But as for me and my house, we will serve the LORD."*⁸⁶

It has always been the prerogative of the government, any government, to regulate killing. Mostly it does a bad job. The least it can do now, is a less bad job.

⁸⁴ Jim Obergefell holds a photo of his late husband John Arthur as he speaks to members of the media in June 2015 outside the US Supreme Court after gay marriage was legalized. (Alex Wong/Getty Images)

⁸⁵ Holy Shoe-horning Batman!

⁸⁶ Joshua 24:15 *"And if it seems evil to you to serve the LORD, choose for yourselves this day whom you will serve, whether the gods which your fathers served that were on the other side of the River, or the gods of the Amorites, in whose land you dwell. But as for me and my house, we will serve the LORD."*